

$a \sin x + b \cos x = c$ KO'RINISHDAGI TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada $a \sin x + b \cos x = c$ ko'rinishidagi trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish usullari haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi. Mazkur turdagi tenglamalarni soddalashtirish, ularni bir jinsli trigonometrik tenglamalarga keltirish hamda yordamchi burchak usulidan foydalanib yechish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, trigonometrik funksiyalar orasidagi bog'lanishlar va almashtirish formulalaridan samarali foydalanish ko'nikmalari shakllantiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: trigonometrik tenglamalar, umumiy yechim, yordamchi burchak usuli, asosiy trigonometrik ayniyatlar, bir jinsli tenglamalar.

Abstract: This article provides information about methods for solving trigonometric equations of the form $a \sin x + b \cos x = c$. The ways of simplifying such equations, reducing them to homogeneous trigonometric equations, and solving them using the auxiliary angle method are analyzed. In addition, skills of effectively using relationships between trigonometric functions and transformation formulas are developed.

Keywords: trigonometric equations, general solution, auxiliary angle method, basic trigonometric identities, homogeneous equations.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются методы решения тригонометрических уравнений вида $a \sin x + b \cos x = c$. Анализируются способы упрощения таких уравнений, приведения их к однородным тригонометрическим уравнениям, а также решения с использованием метода вспомогательного угла. Кроме того, формируются навыки эффективного использования связей между тригонометрическими функциями и формул преобразования.

Ключевые слова: тригонометрические уравнения, общее решение, метод вспомогательного угла, основные тригонометрические тождества, однородные уравнения.

Trigonometrik tenglama va tengsizliklarni yechish jarayonida haqiqiy argumentli trigonometrik funksiyalar va ularning xossalarini, bir xil argumentli trigonometrik funksiyalar orasidagi munosabatlarni, qo'shish teoremlari va ularning natijalarini, trigonometrik funksiyaning ko'paytmasini yig'indiga va aksincha almashtirish formulalariga oid bilimlarni tahlil qila olishi kerak..

Ushbu

$$a \sin x + b \cos x = c \quad (1)$$

ko'rinishdagi tenglamani bir jinsli trigonometrik tenglamaga keltirib yechish mumkin.

Haqiqatdan ham

$$2a \sin \frac{x}{2} \cos \frac{x}{2} + b \left(\cos^2 \frac{x}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{x}{2} \right) = c \left(\cos^2 \frac{x}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{x}{2} \right)$$

hamma hadlarni o'ng tomonga o'tkazib

$$(b+c)\sin^2 \frac{x}{2} - 2a \sin \frac{x}{2} \cos \frac{x}{2} + (c-b)\cos^2 \frac{x}{2} = 0$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Agar $b+c \neq 0$ bo'lsa tenglamaning har ikki qismini $\cos^2 \frac{x}{2} \neq 0$ ga bo'lib unga teng kuchli

$$(c+b)tg^2 \frac{x}{2} - 2atg \frac{x}{2} + (c-b) = 0$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Bundan $tg \frac{x}{2} = \frac{a \pm \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}}{c+b}$.

Agar $a^2 + b^2 > c^2$ bo'lsa, $x = 2arctg \frac{a \pm \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}}{c+b} + 2\pi k; k \in Z$.

Agar $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ bo'lsa, $x = 2arctg \frac{a}{c+b} + 2\pi n; n \in Z$.

Agar $a^2 + b^2 < c^2$ bo'lsa tenglama ildizga ega emas.

Agar $b+c=0$ va $a \neq 0$ bo'lsa $\cos \frac{x}{2} \left((c-b)\cos \frac{x}{2} - 2a \sin \frac{x}{2} \right) = 0$, bundan

$x = \pi + 2\pi k; k \in Z$ va $x = 2arctg \frac{c-b}{2a} + 2\pi l; l \in Z$. Agar $b+c=0$ va $a=0, b=c$

bo'lsa $\cos^2 \frac{x}{2} = 0, x = \pi + 2\pi m; m \in Z$. Bunday tenglamalarni

$$\sin x = \frac{2tg \frac{x}{2}}{1 + tg^2 \frac{x}{2}} \quad \text{va} \quad \cos x = \frac{1 - tg^2 \frac{x}{2}}{1 + tg^2 \frac{x}{2}}$$

formulalarni qo'llab ham yechsa bo'ladi. Bunda $x = \pi + 2\pi k; k \in Z$ berilgan tenglama ildizi bo'lmasligini tekshirib ko'rish kerak.

1-misol. Ushbu tenglamani yeching: $2\sin x + 3\cos x + 3 = 0$

Yechish. $x = \pi + 2\pi n; n \in Z$ tenglamaning ildizi bo'ladi. $x \neq \pi + 2\pi n; n \in Z$ deb

hisoblaymiz va $\sin x, \cos x$ larni $tg \frac{x}{2}$ orqali ifodalab quyidagi tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\frac{4tg \frac{x}{2}}{1 + tg^2 \frac{x}{2}} + \frac{3 - 3tg^2 \frac{x}{2}}{1 + tg^2 \frac{x}{2}} + 3 = 0,$$

$$4tg \frac{x}{2} + 3 - 3tg^2 \frac{x}{2} + 3 + 3tg^2 \frac{x}{2} = 0,$$

$$4tg \frac{x}{2} = -6 \quad \text{va}$$

$x = -2arctg 1,5 + 2\pi n, n \in Z$.

Javob: $\pi + 2\pi k; k \in Z, -2arctg 1,5 + 2\pi n; n \in Z$.

$$a \sin \omega x + b \cos \omega x = c \quad (a^2 + b^2 \neq 0, \omega \neq 0) \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishdagi tenglamalar (9) tenglamaning xususiyligidir. Bunday tenglamalarni universal almashtirish yoki bir jinsli tenglamaga keltirib yechish mumkin. Bunday tenglamalarni yechishning yana bir usuli yordamida burchak kiritish usulini ko'rsatib o'tamiz. $a \sin \omega x + b \cos \omega x = c \quad (a^2 + b^2 \neq 0)$ bo'lsin. Uning har ikki qismini $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$ ga bo'lamiz. U holda

$$\frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \sin \omega x + \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \cos \omega x = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

φ – quyidagi sistemaning biror yechimi bo'lsin.

$$\begin{cases} \cos \varphi = \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \\ \sin \varphi = \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \end{cases}$$

Bu tengliklardan foydalanib tenglamalarni quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz.

$$\sin \omega x \cos \varphi + \cos \omega x \sin \varphi = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}},$$

$$\sin(\alpha + \beta) = \sin \alpha \cos \beta + \cos \alpha \sin \beta \quad \text{formulani} \quad \text{qo'llab}$$

$$\sin(\omega x + \varphi) = \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \text{ tenglamani hosil qilamiz.}$$

$$\text{Agar } \left| \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right| \leq 1, \quad a^2 + b^2 \geq c^2 \text{ bo'lsa tenglama}$$

$$\omega x + \varphi = (-1)^n \arcsin \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} + \pi n; n \in Z$$

yoki

$$x = \frac{(-1)^n}{\omega} \arcsin \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} - \frac{\varphi}{\omega} + \frac{\pi n}{\omega}; n \in Z$$

yechimga ega.

$$\text{Agar } \left| \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right| > 1, \quad a^2 + b^2 < c^2 \text{ bo'lsa tenglama yechimga ega bo'lmaydi.}$$

2-misol. Ushbu tenglamani yeching: $2 \sin 2x + 3 \cos 2x = 1,5$.

Yechish. Yuqorida keltirilgan shakl almashtirishlarni bajaramiz:

$$\sqrt{4+9} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} \sin 2x + \frac{3}{\sqrt{13}} \cos 2x \right) = \frac{3}{2}.$$

$$\frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} = \cos \varphi, \quad \frac{3}{\sqrt{13}} = \sin \varphi \text{ deb belgilash kiritib, } \sin(2x + \varphi) = \frac{3}{2\sqrt{13}} \text{ tenglamani}$$

hosil qilamiz. Bundan

$$2x + \varphi = (-1)^k \arcsin \frac{3}{2\sqrt{13}} + \pi k; k \in Z,$$

$$x = -\frac{\varphi}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(-1)^k \arcsin \frac{3}{2\sqrt{13}} + \frac{\pi k}{2}; k \in Z.$$

φ burchak o'rniga $\arccos \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}}$ yoki $\arcsin \frac{3}{\sqrt{13}}$ ni olamiz. ($\sin \varphi > 0$, $\cos \varphi > 0$ va φ – birinchi chorak burchagi).

$$\text{Javob: } -\frac{1}{2} \arccos \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} + \frac{1}{2}(-1)^k \arcsin \frac{3}{2\sqrt{13}} + \frac{\pi k}{2}; k \in Z$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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